

An Observational Study on Intestinal Obstruction at Tertiary Care Hospital of North East India

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Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 25-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Intestinal obstruction (IO) is one of the most common surgical emergency worldwide which is predisposed by varying underlying anomalies and diseases, which are difficult to define preoperatively. Since there was lack of data of IO in north eastern part of India hence we planned to determine the causes of intestinal obstruction, clinical presentation and age related factors and management of intestinal obstruction which might give insight for better patient outcome.

Materials and Methods: The present study was a Prospective observational study which was conducted from December 2022 to November 2023 at Department of General Surgery in tertiary care hospital of Assam, India. Total 60 patients with clinical and radiological findings of IO were included in this study.

Results: The study showed peak incidence of IO in the age group of 31- 40 years of 21.7% and 41 to 50 years of 21.7 %. The male to female ratio was 1.14:1. In our study, Majority of patients presented with Pain abdomen 57 (95.0%) and distension 53(88.3%). most common diagnosis in IO was adhesion which were present in 31.7% patients whereas Mesenteric ischemia were only in 1.7 % patients. The most common USG findings was Distended small bowel (DSB) which were present in 40.0% patients. Majority of patients (28.4 %) were treated conservatively and 71.6% patient of the IO undergone operative procedure, among which 18% underwent adhesiolysis, 20% underwent Resection and anastomosis.

Conclusion: Early recognition and aggressive treatment are crucial in preventing irreversible ischemia and transmural necrosis and thereby in decreasing mortality and long-term morbidity. The evaluation of patients with suspected bowel obstruction endeavours not only to confirm the diagnosis but also to determine the need for and timing of surgery.

Keywords: Intestinal Obstruction, Acute Small Bowel Obstruction, India.

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Introduction

Intestinal obstruction (IO) is one of the most common surgical emergencies worldwide. It is defined as an obstruction in forward propulsion of the contents in the intestine caused by mechanical or neurological factors. It is predisposed by varying underlying anomalies and diseases, which are difficult to define preoperatively [1]. It is common in low and middle income countries, accounting for 1.8 deaths per 100,000 populations per year. It accounts for 50 percent of emergency laparotomies each year in UK and over 300,000 admissions

annually in USA. The prevalence of IO in India is 12 - 16% as a whole [2]. IO may be classified into two types, first is Dynamic, in which peristalsis is working against a mechanical obstruction which may occur in an acute or a chronic form. Second is Adynamic, in which there is no mechanical obstruction; peristalsis is absent or inadequate. As far as location is concerned, IO may be two types. Acute small bowel obstruction can be caused by a variety of factors, ranging from common causes such as adhesions, hernias, and cancer to

uncommon conditions such as intussusceptions. Large bowel obstruction, defined as the bowel obstruction distal to the ileocecal valve, can occur as a result of variety of etiologies. Most common causes are volvulus and colorectal cancers. The classic presentation is abdominal pain, vomiting, constipation, and distension; diagnosis requires a thorough understanding of surgical anatomy, pathophysiology, sign and symptoms of obstruction, and the necessary investigation. The management of the intestinal obstruction has shifted more to conservative care with nasogastric tube decompression and rehydration. The operative intervention is reserved for those who fails conservative management and have evidence of vascular compromise, strangulations, or perforation [3]. Although mortality from acute intestinal obstruction is decreasing due to a better understanding of pathophysiology, advancements in diagnostic techniques, fluid and electrolyte correction, more potent antimicrobials, and intensive care knowledge. In small bowel obstruction, the dictum of never letting the sun set or rise has resulted in early surgical intervention for intestinal obstruction [4].

This study seeks to evaluate the causes of intestinal obstructions in different age groups and early management of the patient according to the cause. As, early detection of obstruction, skilled operative management, proper technique during surgery, and intensive postoperative care yield a positive outcome. Since there was lack of data of IO in north eastern part of India hence we planned to determine the causes of intestinal obstruction, clinical presentation and age related factors and management of intestinal obstruction which might give insight for better patient outcome

Materials and Methods

The present study comprised of 60 patients with intestinal obstruction and treated in the Department of Surgery at Jorhat Medical College and Hospital, Jorhat, during the period from December 2022 to November 2023. The Study Design is Hospital based Prospective Observational Study. The Data were collected in a pretested Proforma of patients with Intestinal Obstruction. The Ethical clearance was obtained from Institutional Ethics Committee of Jorhat Medical College, Jorhat before enrolment of the patients in the study. The purposive sampling was done through the medical records of our hospital; approximately 50-70 cases of IO were admitted in Surgery department in each year for last 3 years hence the expected sample size was calculated 60 for study duration of one year. The Selection of case was made on the basis of history, clinical features, with radiological evidence as well as laparotomy findings during operation. The inclusion criteria were ; Dynamic small bowel and large bowel obstruction, age more than 12 years

and patients who have given written informed consent and exclusion criteria were ; Adynamic small bowel and large bowel obstruction. The functional outcome was assessed at the time of discharge from the hospital.

On admission of the patients to the surgery ward, a detailed history was obtained with special reference to the presence of pain abdomen, vomiting, abdominal distension and constipation. Patients are also enquired about previous treatment history, previous abdominal surgery. History of other medical diseases like heart disease, CVA, diabetes, liver and kidney diseases, metastatic disease, were taken.

Examination findings like Temperature, Pulse rate, Blood pressure. Respiratory rate, visible peristalsis, abdominal tenderness, guarding, rigidity, significant per rectal findings and groin swelling are recorded. Physical examination to detect any features of SIRS, sepsis, shock and organ dysfunction was done

Initial Resuscitation and Management: Immediately after diagnosis, all the patients along with the above procedure, were given proper care and resuscitation as needed in the casualty department. All the patients were resuscitated with intravenous fluids like Ringer lactate or Normal saline till the hydration and urine output becomes normal. Nasogastric tube decompression with insertion of long Ryle's tube, per urethra Foley's catheterization were carried out. All the patients were administered analgesics, antispasmodic, proton pump inhibitors, and antibiotics. Most patients were given either ceftriaxone or piperacillin with metronidazole. All the patients were kept Nil Per Orally. A close observation of all bedside parameters (like pulse rate, BP, RR, urine output, abdominal girth, bowel sounds, tenderness and guarding) were done. Emergency Blood transfusion was given in required case. All patients were corrected for dehydration, electrolyte imbalance, anaemia and made fit for anaesthesia and surgery [5-6].

Patients who showed a reduction in the abdominal distension and improvement in the general condition especially in those with postoperative adhesions [7], conservative treatment was confined (by extending the supportive treatment) for next 24 hours, those patients who showed clinical improvement by return of bowels movement, reduction in pain/tenderness and abdominal distension were considered for further conservative treatment. Patients with clear-cut signs and symptoms of acute obstruction or with features of strangulation and those failed to respond to conservative treatment had been managed by appropriate surgical procedure after initial resuscitation. Surgery adopted and the criteria for

deciding the procedure were noted, e.g. release of a band or an adhesion [8], reduction for obstructed hernia, intussusception, resection and anastomosis for gangrenous intestine and release with repair for strangulated obstruction. Histo-pathological examination of the specimen of resection/ biopsy was undertaken whenever needed.

The statistical software namely SPSS 27.0 was used for the analysis of the data.

Results

In our study, Majority of patients 26 (43.4%) were between 31-50 years of age group and males 32 (53.3%) were more than 28 (46.7%) female patients. (Table-1 & 2)

Table 1: Distribution of Age among participants

S.No.	Age in year	Frequency	Percent	Statistics
1	12-20	5	8.3%	value of z is 2.6854 and p is .00714
2	21-30	12	20.0%	
3	31-40	13	21.7%	
4	41-50	13	21.7%	
5	51-60	6	10.0%	
6	61-70	8	13.3%	
7	≥71	3	5.0%	
	Total	60	100.0%	

Table 2: Distribution of Sex among participants

S.No.	Sex	Frequency	Percent	Statistics
1	Female	28	46.7%	Value of z is 0.7303. The value of p is 0.4654
2	Male	32	53.3%	
	Total	60	100.0%	

In our study, Majority of patients presented with Pain abdomen 57 (95.0%) and distension 53(88.3%). (Table-3)

Table 3: Distribution of Pain abdomen and Distension among participants

S.No.	Pain abdomen	Frequency (%)	Statistics	Distension	Frequency	Statistics
1	Absent	3 (5.0%)	z is 9.859 p is < 0.00001	Absent	7(11.7%)	z is 8.3984 p is < 0.00001
2	Present	57 (95.0%)		Present	53(88.3%)	
	Total	60 (100.0%)		Total	60(100.0%)	

The USG findings have been shown in **Table-4** where most common finding was Distended small bowel (DSB) which were present in 40.0% patients whereas DSB with Right obstructed inguinal hernia and Intussusception, Ilio-colic were only in 1 % patients

Table 4: Distribution of USG among participants

USG	Frequency	Percent	Statistics
Distended large Bowel, Colonic dilatation	2	3.3%	The value of z is 5.17 & p is < .00001
DSB (Distended small bowel)	24	40.0%	
DSB, Adhesion	4	6.7%	
DSB, Bands in ileum	3	5.0%	
DSB, Growth in ascending colon	2	1.7%	
DSB, Ileal growth	2	3.3%	
DSB, Ileocaecal inflamed	7	11.7%	
DSB, Left obstructed inguinal hernia	6	10%	
DSB, Growth in ileocaecal junction	2	3.3%	
DSB, Right obstructed inguinal hernia	1	1.7%	
DSB, Right inguinal hernia	1	1.7%	
DSB, Right sided strangulated hernia	3	5.0%	
DSB, Intussusception(ileo-ileal)	2	3.3%	
Intussusception, Ilio-colic	1	1.7%	
Total	60	100.0%	

In our study, 20 (33.3%) patients had distended small bowel (DSB) and 40 (66.7%) patients had multiple air fluid level (MAF). (Table 5)

Table 5: Distribution of X-Ray PP Abdomen among participants

S.No.	X-Ray PP Abdomen	Frequency	Percent	Statistics
1	DSB	20	33.3%	The value of z is 3.6515 & p is 0.00026
2	MAF	40	66.7%	
	Total	60	100.0%	

The all Diagnosis have been shown in Table-6 where most common was adhesion which were present in 31.7% patients whereas Mesenteric ischemia were only in 1.7 % patients

Table 6 : Distribution of Diagnosis among participants

Diagnosis	Frequency	Percent	Statistics
Abdominal Koch	7	11.7%	The value of z is 4.4091 & p is < 0.00001
Adhesion	19	31.7%	
Bands	5	8.3%	
Inguinal hernia	11	18.3%	
Intussusception	3	5.0%	
Malignancy	6	10.0%	
Meckel's diverticulum	4	6.7%	
Mesenteric ischemia	1	1.7%	
Sigmoid volvulus	2	3.3%	
Stricture	2	3.3%	
Total	60	100.0%	

As per Table-7, the conservative, R&A, Herniorrhaphy were the main management done for majority of patients.

Table 7: Distribution of Management of IO among participants

Management	Frequency	Percent	Statistics
Adhesiolysis	11	18.3%	The value of z is 3.0363 & p is .00236
Band Release	5	8.3%	
Conservative	13	21.7%	
Conservative (ATT)	4	6.7%	
Hernioplasty	2	3.3%	
Ileostomy	4	6.7%	
R&A	12	20.0%	
R&A, Herniorrhaphy	9	15.0%	
Total	60	100.0%	

Discussion

Bowel obstruction continues to be one of the most common abdominal problems faced by general surgeons. Irrespective of the cause, it remains a major cause of morbidity and mortality. In our study, intussusception and abdominal koch were more prevalent in younger age group from 12 to 30 years of age; inguinal hernia and bowel malignancy were prevalent in elderly age group from 50 years of age and above, whereas adhesions was found to be the most common cause of intestinal obstruction among all age group. Among adhesions, majority of cases had previous history of abdominal surgery.

Age incidence

Intestinal obstruction although occurs in all age groups, the age spectrum in our study was above 12 years. The study showed peak incidence in the age group of 31- 40 years of 21.7% and 41 to 50 years of 21.7 % which is comparable with the previous study done by Adhikari S et al [9] in which peak incidence was in age group of 41-50 years (24%)

and a study done by Cole GJ et al [10] in which the peak incidence in age group 31-40 years (18%)

Sex incidence

In study by Adhikari S et al, male is to female ratio was 4:1. In study by Osuigwe AN et al [11], male is to female ratio us 2:1. In our study male is to female ratio was 1.14:1.

Clinical features

In our study, common clinical features of intestinal obstruction are abdominal pain, abdominal distension, vomiting and constipation. Pain abdomen was present in 95% of the case in our study. Distension of abdomen was present in 88% of the cases. Vomiting was present in 86% of the cases, whereas constipation was present in 30 % of the cases which can be compared to a study done by Adhikari S et al.[9] where they found around 72% of the cases presented with pain abdomen 91% with vomiting, 93% with abdominal distension and 82% of the patients presented with constipation.

Apart from this study, an study conducted by Jahangir-Sarwar Khan et al [12] where they found pain abdomen in 100% of the patients, 92% with vomiting, 97% with distension and 97% with constipation.

Radiological findings

In our study, 95% of the cases had small bowel distension in USG finding and 3.3% had large bowel distension. In X-Ray PP abdomen, 33% had distended small bowel, 66% of the cases had multiple air fluid level.

Etiology

The causes of intestinal obstruction differ in different geographical region. In present study, 7(11.7%) patients had abdominal koch, 19 (31.7%) patients hadadhesion, 5(8.3%) patients hadbands, 11(18.3%) patients had inguinal hernia ,3(5.0%) patients hadintussusception, 6(10.0%) patients hadmalignancy, 4(6.7%) patients had meckel's diverticulum, 1(1.7%) patients had mesenteric ischemia, 2(3.3%) patients had sigmoid volvulus and 2(3.3%) patients had stricture. (Table 8)

Table 8: Comparison of our study with other studies in reference to etiology.

Diagnosis	Present Study	Adhikari S ⁹	Jahangir ¹²	Cole GJ ¹⁰
Abdominal Koch	11.7%	14%	1%	3%
Adhesion	31.7%	16%	49%	10%
Bands	8.3%	-	-	-
Inguinal hernia	18.3%	36%	34%	35%
Intussusception	5.0%	2%	6%	9%
Malignancy	10.0%	17%	3%	12%
Meckel's diverticulum	6.7%	-	-	-
Mesenteric ischemia	1.7%	9%	2%	-
Sigmoid volvulus	3.3%	6%	5%	3%

Management: In our study, out of 60 patients 28.4% of the patients were treated conservatively and 71.6% patient of the intestinal obstruction had to undergo operative procedure, among which 18% underwent adhesiolysis, 20% underwent Resection and anastomosis which were comparable with previous studies done by Adhikari S [9] and Cole GJ [10].

Conclusion

From our study, we can conclude that, while taking history and performing clinical examination, we should primarily focus on the respective etiologies of the susceptible age groups, for finding the causes and treat the patient accordingly.

Success in the treatment of intestinal obstruction depends largely upon early diagnosis, skillful management and treating the pathological effects of the obstruction just as much as the cause itself. Early recognition and aggressive treatment are crucial in preventing irreversible ischemia and transmural necrosis and thereby in decreasing mortality and long-term morbidity. The evaluation of patients with suspected bowel obstruction endeavors not only to confirm the diagnosis but also to determine the need for and timing of surgery.

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